

STUDY OF INTERFACIAL BEHAVIOR OF CNT/POLYMER COMPOSITE BY CFE METHOD

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Keywords: *CNT/polymer composite, interfacial behavior, cohesive finite element*

1 Introduction

Since its discovery by Iijima in 1991 [1], carbon nanotube (CNT) has been expected to have many potential applications inspired by their superb physical and mechanical properties. However, the unavoidable poor interfacial strength between CNTs and polymers has been hindering their composites to fully achieve the desired mechanical properties. To put forward an effective solution, a number of atomic simulation methods have been implemented to study the CNT/polymer interface [2-4]. However, there is a hard barrier for these methods to study the macroscopic interface because of their huge calculation cost. Therefore, a proper method in macroscopic scale, which can help study the performance of the CNT/polymer interface, is necessary. In this paper, a cohesive zone model (CZM) in continuum finite element (CFE) method was adopted to investigate the deformation and fracture process of the interface between CNT and the epoxy matrix. The interface performance of the composite was discussed in transverse and longitudinal models separately. The influence of the interface characteristics on the effective mechanical properties of the CNT/polymer composite was analyzed in both cases. Furthermore, the effect of CNT arrangement on the interfacial fracture mechanism and effective mechanical properties of the CNT/polymer composite were also considered.

2 CFE model

It is well known that van der Waals (vdW) forces among atoms plays a dominating role in the shear strength of the nano-scopic interface of the CNT reinforced composites. Practically, at the continuum scale, the vdW forces in the interface sum up to cohesive forces, which can be described by a CZM model [5]. In FEM method, the CZM model can be used to describe material separation by a traction-separation law (T-S law) and reflect the local interface failures to the effective properties of the

whole composite. Therefore, the characteristics and functions of the vdW forces in the interfaces between a CNT and polymer can be well represented by two parameters in the CZM model, i.e. the cohesive strength T_c and the energy release rate G_c [6]. The energy release rate of the interface represents the energy dissipation during damage and failure process of the material. The bilinear T-S law of the CZM model used in this paper is shown in Fig.1. In this image, δ_0 denotes an interface separation distance at which the interfacial stress reaches its cohesive strength T_c . And δ_f denotes an interface separation distance at which the cohesive force vanishes. Tan et al. [5] deduced the cohesive strength of 470Mpa and the energy release rate of 0.107Jm^{-2} of the interfaces in CNT reinforced composites from atomic calculation results by using Lennard-Jones potential. In this paper, these two values were referenced as basic parameter values.

Figure 1 Bilinear T-S law used in the CZM model

The CFE model of the CNT reinforced composite was established by the generally used software ABAQUS. The present model consists three phases: the CNT phase, the cohesive interface phase (described by the CZM model) and the polymer matrix phase. Since the interface is the primary concern in this paper, the CNT was simply treated as a uniform fiber without cavity and the polymer is considered as an even material. The Young's

modules of the CNT and the epoxy matrix are taken as 1 TPa and 4GPa, respectively. In the following parts, transverse and longitudinal models of the CNT/polymer composite were built and analyzed separately.

3 Debonding simulation of the transverse model

The transverse model of a continuous CNT/polymer composite was simplified to a quarter model, as shown in Fig. 2. Normal extension was exerted on the right boundary of the unit cell, while the two symmetry boundaries sides were fixed in their normal directions.

Figure 2 Three-phase transverse quarter model of CNT/polymer composite

In this paper, the interface is said to start yielding when its von Mises stress reaches the critical value known as the yield strength, T_c . Based on the stress distribution in the meshed model, the deformation process can be divided to stages: the linear elastic stage, the damage accumulation stage and the crack propagation stage. Typical stress distributions of the model in three stages are plotted in Fig. 3. In the linear elastic stage, the epoxy matrix and the CNT are well bonded by the intact interface, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The stresses in the matrix are mainly distributed around a part of the CNT cross-section that is perpendicular to the tension direction. Then through the perfect interface, most of the stresses are transferred to the nearby CNT section. Therefore, CNT takes more loads than the matrix in this stage, giving rise to reinforcement of the composite. The second stage begins with the first debonding of the node at where the interface perpendicular to the external loading. Afterwards, the interface is striped off node by node from the first debonded node as the stresses on them reach the cohesive strength. As a result, debonded nodes on the interface induce stress redistribution in the composite, as illustrated in Fig.

3(b). Once the interface is broken in some nodes, the stresses near the debonded nodes in the matrix are much smaller and even zero. At the same time, the stresses are concentrated near the crack tip and the boundary of the matrix, which promotes the crack propagation in return. Though, a lot of the stresses are still transferred to the inner CNT through the undamaged part of the interface. In the third stage, as seen in Fig. 3(c), a large part of the interface between the matrix and CNT are striped off. As a result, the stresses are barely transferred to the inner CNT, leaving the stresses were solely centralized at the crack tip. It is noticed that the bearing capacity of the composite is remarkably reduced, although there are also residual strength and rigidity.

Figure 3 Stress distribution of interfacial debonding process: a) linear elastic stage, b) damage accumulation and crack initial stage, c) crack propagation stage

To describe the debonding process of the interface nodes, scalar damage variable D is adopted. It is defined that the cohesive elements are all undamaged when D is equals to 0, while the cohesive elements are totally damaged when D is equals to 1. So, when D is a value between 0 to 1, the cohesive elements are partly damaged, indicating that the interface still has load bearing capacity. The failure process of one single node in the interface is expressly illustrated in Fig. 4. As the separation distance at this node increases, the cohesive stress develops until it reaches the cohesive strength T_c . The value of D keeps the constant of 0, representing the interface at this node is intact in this stage. After the point, the value of D increases over time accompanied with gradual drop

in stress, indicating the damage propagates. At last, when the value of D tops 1, the interface is fully deboned at this node and the local fracture is occurred.

Figure 4 Failure process of a single node

4 Effect of CZM parameters on mechanical properties of the transverse model

The stress-strain curve of the transverse unit cell of the composite is depicted in Fig. 5. Due to the effect of the interface, the whole relation between stress and strain of the transverse model is nonlinear. Firstly, the stress is increased nonlinearly with the strain to an ultimate strength about 0.374GPa at a strain of 0.092. The effective transverse module of the model is calculated as 6.7 GPa, showing a remarkable reinforcement to the matrix. Secondly, after the ultimate strain, the stress is partly reduced as the strain increases, which expresses that the composite material is weakened. After stress redistribution as mentioned above, the composite material still has a certain load bearing capacity unless the interface is completely deboned. Therefore, the failure mode of the CNT reinforced composite under transverse force is plastic.

Figure 5 Stress-strain relation of the transverse model

Since the mechanical properties of the interface in the model is controlled by two key parameters: cohesive strength τ_c and energy release rate G_c , parametric study was implemented to study the impact of these two interface parameters on the mechanical properties of the CNT composites.

Firstly, the energy release rate on the mechanical properties of the composite is analyzed. The cohesive strength τ_c is taken as a constant of 470MPa and the value of energy release rate are 0.107N/m, 0.05 N/m and 0.2 N/m, respectively. The stress-strain curve of the model with different energy release rate is depicted in Fig. 6. The stress-strain relations of the composite before ultimate strength are completely unaffected by the energy release rate as seen from the overlap part of the three curves. However, the ultimate stress and strain of the composite are reduced by the energy release rate obviously. In addition, the lower the energy release rate, the larger the stress drop after the ultimate strain.

When G_c is 0.05, the ultimate stress is about 0.35GPa at a strain of 0.06. Then, the stress drops by almost 50% to 1.75GPa at strain of 0.07, showing a feature of brittle fracture. However, after that, the stress is slightly increased with the strain.

When G_c is 0.17, due to the increase of the energy release rate, a larger interfacial opening displacement is imperative for the failure by the debonding, the energy dissipated during the failure process of interface increases. So, when the stress reaches its maximum value of 0.385GPa at strain of 0.07, a short plateau is shown on the stress-strain curve. Along with the interfacial crack propagation, the effective stress experiences a gentle downward trend, then stay stable at the value of about 80% of the maximum stress.

When G_c is increased to 0.2, the interfacial micro-crack initiates more slowly on account of the large energy release rate, and the interface crack is not easily to extend. Moreover, a soften stage takes place in the stress-strain curve. After the stress reaches its maximum value, it is gradually decreased with the increase of the strain. That means, a larger the energy release rate can ensure a higher toughness and residual carrying capacity of the composites.

After the analysis on the effect of energy release rate, its value is kept as a constant of 0.107 to discuss the effect of another parameter, namely cohesive strength, on the mechanical properties of the CNT/polymer composite. The stress-strain curves of the transverse model with different interface

cohesive strength of 370MPa, 470MPa and 570MPa are illustrated in Fig.7. It is clearly shown that the maximum stress is enlarged with the value of T_c , demonstrating a significantly positive correlation between strength of the composite and its interfacial cohesive strength. However, the critical strain where the stress tops the maximum value in the transverse model is independent of the interface cohesive strength due to the constant energy release rate. Besides the critical strain, the residual carrying capacity of the composite is not affected by the cohesive strength, either. After the interface crack propagation, the stress-strain curves of the models with T_c of 470MPa and 570MPa are even overlap with each other. From the results, it is demonstrated that the strength of the CNT composites is dependent, to a large extent, on the strength of the interface, which is in accord with the existing experimental data and atomic simulation results. Therefore, the present CZM model can be effectively and easily used to predict the strength and mechanical properties of the CNT composite material with interfaces of different cohesive strength.

Figure 6 Stress vs. strain of the transverse model with different energy release rate

Figure 7 Stress vs. strain of the transverse model with different cohesive strength

5 Effect of CNT volume fraction on mechanical properties of the transverse model

The volume fraction of CNT, V_f , is a key factor that dominates the mechanical properties of CNT composites. Hence, the role of V_f to stress transfer performance and effective mechanical properties of the composite is also studied in the present model. The value of the V_f is taken as 19.6%, 28.3%, and 38.5%, respectively. The stress-strain curves of the corresponding models are illustrated in Fig.8. In the first stage, as the interfaces in three models are all under perfect condition, the slope of the stress-strain curve is positively associated with the volume fraction of CNT. That means, the elastic modulus derived from these curves also show a remarkable positive correlation with the volume fraction of the CNT. Then in the second stage, it is noticed that the ultimate strength is barely affected by the volume fraction, while the ultimate strain is remarkably reduced by the CNT volume fraction. Another difference is found in the third stage of the curves, namely the residual carrying capacity of composites after reaching the ultimate stress. For the composite with a higher volume fraction of CNT, it needs a larger strain increment to release the stress. Consequently, in the transverse model, the volume fraction of the CNT helps improve the effective elastic modulus of the composite at the expense of ultimate strain although the stress release rate is decreased to make up the extensibility of the composite.

Figure 8 Stress vs. strain of the transverse model with different volume fraction

6 Effect of CNT radial deformation on mechanical properties of the longitudinal model

In CNT reinforced composites, almost of the CNTs were found to have ellipse cross-sections and even

dog-bone shape cross-sections rather than circle ones. In fact, for a single-walled CNT (SWCNT) with radius larger than 1.05 nm, the cross-section will collapse owing to the large-enough vdW forces. The larger the SWCNT radius, the easier for the SWCNT to collapse. Actually, for SWCNTs with radius larger than 1.90 nm, the collapsed states are more stable [7]. The radial deformation of CNT plays a significant role in affecting mechanical behavior of CNT composite [8]. So, the ellipse cross-section was introduced in the transverse model [9]. Fig.9 provides three full transverse schematic models in which the inner CNTs have different length-width ratios of 1:1, 2:1 and 3:1. The volume fraction of the CNT is fixed as 28.3% in three models, so the size of the matrix surrounding the CNT varies with the volume fraction of the CNT.

Figure 9 RVEs of CNT composites with different length-width ratio of the CNT cross-section

Uniform tensions were applied on the models along the length and the width directions of the CNT cross-section, separately. And the stress-strain curves are plotted in Figs. 10 and 11.

For the first case, as shown in stress-strain curves in Fig.10, the strength and linear elastic modulus of composite are increased with the increase of the length-width ratio of CNT cross-section. For the other case, the stress-strain curves are shown in Fig.11. As can be seen, the strength and linear elastic modulus of composite are decreased with the increase of the length-width ratio of CNT cross-section, which is contrary to the first case. However, elastic modulus of the composite in the second case is almost unaffected by the ratio, while the residual carrying capacity of the composite material is enhanced with the length-width ratio.

Figure 10 Stress vs. strain of the transverse models in the length direction of the CNT cross-section

Figure 11 Stress vs. strain of the transverse models in the width direction of the CNT cross-section

Briefly, the radial deformation of CNT causes anisotropic mechanical properties in transverse models of the composite. The mechanical performance of CNT composite in the length direction of the CNT cross-section is enhanced while the mechanical performance in the width direction of the CNT cross-section is weakened.

7 Debonding simulation of the longitudinal model

As micro-scale reinforcements in polymer, the CNTs may have different shapes as well as arrangements, which have significant influence on the effective mechanical properties of the composite. Therefore, four typical array patterns and three representative cross-sections of the CNT are considered in the following longitudinal models. Other parameters, i.e. aspect ratio and volume fraction of the CNT, are invariant in the simulations.

Figure 12 Four typical array patterns of CNT in CNT/polymer and their RVE: a) regular array, b) end-to-end array, c) staggered array and d) spaced array

In Fig.12, four schematic composite models with four typical array patterns of CNTs are listed. Because of the periodicity, simulations can be employed on their representative volume elements (RVEs) as seen in the red boxes. And for the sake of simplification, half models of RVEs were utilized, as plotted in Fig.13.

Figure 13 Half models of the RVEs: a) regular array, b) end-to-end array, c) staggered array and d) spaced array

The stress distributions of the models in this stage are listed in Figs. 14 (a) to (d), respectively. The stress concentration in the CNTs indicates that after interface is damaged on the CNT ends, the stresses can still be transferred in the CNTs through the side interfaces. And the maximum stress is larger when the gap between CNT ends is smaller. That means the staggered CNTs in the composite have the

maximum stress at this time. In short, the gap size between CNT ends plays a significant role in stress distribution and redistribution processes.

Figure 14 Stress distribution during the crack propagation process: a) regular array, b) end-to-end array, c) staggered array and d) spaced array

To further discuss the effect of the CNT arrangements, the stress-strain curves of the models are illustrated in Fig.15. Because of the effect of the interface strength, the relation between stress and strain is nonlinear, as discussed above. But at first, the curves display linear characters, on account of the full effect of the interface before the stresses get to their maximum values. The slopes of these curves are close, however, the ultimate strain of the longitudinal model varies with the gap size. It is interesting to find that the failure mode of the composite is severely influenced by the CNT array patterns. To be specific, the present models with end-to-end array and spaced array of CNTs both have a sudden drop in stress after beyond strength, while the models with other two array patterns of CNTs have a clear stress plateau. The performance of the interface determines the mechanical property of the CNT composites.

The elastic modulus can be deduced from the slopes of the curves in the first stage in Fig. 15 and

illustrated in histograms in Fig. 16. The model with staggered array of CNTs has the highest elastic modulus, while the one with spaced array of CNTs has the lowest elastic modulus, which indicates a clear negative correlation between gap size and the elastic modulus. The results demonstrate that decreasing the size of gaps between CNTs in the composites is important in improving their overall mechanical properties.

Figure 15 Stress-strain curves of longitudinal models with different CNT arrangements

Figure 16 Effective elastic modulus of composites with four types of CNT arrangements

The strength the composite models with different CNT arrangements are listed in Table 1. The end-to-end array of CNT causes serious stress concentration, which speeds up the interfacial failure process, so its strength is the lowest. On contrary, the composite model with staggered array of CNTs possesses the largest strength thanks to the better stress redistribution mechanism. The other two composite models have moderate strength as well as ultimate

strain shown in Fig. 15.

In short, the array pattern of CNTs in the composites plays a significant role in determining the stress distribution mechanism, strength, elastic modulus as well as the failure mode. The results provide proofs to the advantages of using staggered CNT array in the composites.

Table1 Max stress of the composite with different array patterns of CNTs

Array patterns	Strength (GPa)
Spaced array	0.261
Regular array	0.303
End-to-end array	0.212
Staggered array	0.322

8 Conclusion

In brief, the simulation results of the present models with cohesive interface verify that the CFE can be effectively used to describe the CNT/polymer composites. The effect of interface properties on the macroscopic mechanical behavior of the composite was studied by stress-strain curves, and the mechanical behaviors of composites with different arrangements and shapes of CNTs were investigated as well.

- (1) CZM is an effective model for describing the cohesive force, sum of vdW forces, in the interfaces.
- (2) The whole deformation and damage process of the interface was studied through the simulation results. The performance of the interface plays an important role in improving the mechanical properties of the CNT composites.
- (3) The strength of the CNT composites is determined by the strength of the interface, while the failure mode of CNT composites is influenced by energy release rate.
- (4) The increase of volume fraction of CNT can help improve the effective modulus of the composite, while the composite is weakened when the interfacial debonding occurs.
- (5) The radial deformation of CNT causes anisotropic mechanical properties in transverse models of the composite.
- (6) The array pattern of CNT in matrix was proved to be a key factor to the mechanical behavior of CNT composites, and the staggered array is the best choice for reinforcement of composites.

References

- [1] Iijima S. Helical microtubules of graphite carbon. *Nature*, Vol .354, pp56-61,1991.
- [2] Gou J H, Minaie B, Wang B, et al. Computational and experimental study of interfacial banding of single-walled nano-tube reinforced composites. *Computational Material Science*, 31,pp225-236,2004.
- [3] Xiao J R, Lopatnikov S L, Gamaa B A, et al. Nano-mechanics on the deformation of single and multi-walled carbon nano-tubes under radial pressure . *Materials Science and Engineering A*, 416,pp192-204,2006.
- [4] Li C Y, Chou T W. Modeling of elastic buckling of carbon nano-tubes by molecular Structural mechanics approach. *Mechanics of Materials*, 36, pp1047-1055,2004
- [5] H.Tan, L.Y.Jiang, Y.Huang, et al. The effect of van der Waals-based interface cohesive law on carbon nanotube-reinforced composite materials. *Composites Science and Technology*, 67,pp2941-2946,2007
- [6] X. Guo, aA.Y.T. Leung and A.Y. Chen: Investigation of non-local cracking in layered stainless steel with nanostructured interface.*Scripta Materialia*, 63, pp403-407,2010
- [7] Elliott, J. A, Sandler, J. K., Windle, A. H., et al. Collapse of Single-Wall Carbon Nanotubes Is Diameter Dependent. *Phys.Rev. Lett.* 92, 095501, 2004.
- [8] Ruoff.R.S, Tersoff,.R.S.; Lorents.D. C, et al. Radial Deformation of Carbon Nanotubes by vander Waals Forces. *Nature*, 364, pp514–516, 1993
- [9] O.Gulseren, T.Yildirim, S. Ciraci,, et al.. Reversible band-gap engineering in carbon nanotubes by radial deformation. *PHYSICAL REVIEW B*, 65,155410, 2002